

Seeing Destinations through Vlogs in the Philippines during the Pandemic

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Abstract: Our study focuses on travel during the pandemic, which occurred in 2020. It displays how travel has changed as a result of travel restrictions in some areas. Traveling is more complicated and costly. The study shows at how we view places through vlogs. Was the situation different before the COVID-19 pandemic? The researchers used qualitative research and observed the 15 videos below.

Keywords: travel restrictions, COVID-19 pandemic?,

1. INTRODUCTION

After more than a year, the shadow of this unprecedented public health crisis still looms all over the world. At the beginning of 2020, the World Health Organization declared a contagious disease caused by a new strain of virus called Coronavirus Disease 2019 or more commonly known as COVID-19 as a global public health emergency, making it an international concern. On March 11, 2020, the Coronavirus was declared a global pandemic. The number of COVID-19 cases continues to grow day by day, because of this the world has adapted to a different kind of 'normal'. The COVID-19 Pandemic has greatly changed how the world works, and travelling has been banned in most countries. As Tourism is solely dependent on travelling, it is one of the most affected industries.

The Tourism of countries has gone down and this has affected many airlines and carriers across the world. Travel vloggers and influencers are not an exemption to this. As there are travel restrictions in place, it is much harder and more expensive to go around places, even places within the country. A lot of cities have been closing off their borders to outsiders and most hotels, restaurants, and tourist attractions are closed. For most Travel Vloggers and Influencers, documenting their travels are their only means of income. This has had a significant impact on their lifestyle and mental health.

As this is their main source of income, Travel Vloggers have found different ways to adapt. At the beginning of 2021, some countries started to open their borders and lessen their restrictions. This has let Travel Vloggers and Influencers to slowly go back to their previous lifestyle. In the Philippines, cities have started letting in outsiders, which has been a great chance for vloggers to create new material. Most countries have also started COVID-19 vaccination, and are hopeful that cases will start to go down once the majority of the population has been vaccinated. Currently, the world is still in a continuous cycle of trying to fight off the pandemic while slowly recovering.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND CONCEPTUAL/THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The authors' research (Arora & Lata) discovered that visitors use their critical thinking abilities and the ability to analyze a travel vlogger's material on YouTube. According to the writers, vloggers who retain or create vlogs for visitors should include information that is relevant, thorough, and factual about the place. Coronavirus has left travel vloggers scrambling, from freedom of movement to income streams, and the virus's impacts will certainly continue to cause them problems long after we are no longer under lockdown. All travel and freedom of movement have come to a halt due to global lockdowns. No new travel contents. Their earnings come from a variety of sources, including photographs, writing and posting, content creation, and social media sharing. Vloggers must be able to travel in order to provide new information on topics such as food, culture, and travel. Additional to it is that there would be no travel related income since majority of travel vloggers' income comes from social media ads and promotion. (Legarda, 2020.) Travel influencers and the COVID crisis. In the travel sector, influencers are acquiring increasing power. However, several of them have recently tarnished their image by traveling despite the coronavirus outbreak. The coronavirus, like so many others, has taken travel influencers of their livelihoods. International travel is almost impossible and advertising partners have drastically scaled back their orders. Many of them now advertise fashion, or mail-order companies. But some influencers carry on regardless. Clients around the world are using them and their immense influence to market travel destinations — especially during the COVID crisis. (Schlagwein, 2021)

Theoretical Framework

by Aurora & Lata (2020)

Figure 1

The researchers are adapting significant predictors according to Arora & Lata (2020). We are using this framework to be utilised in this research, with an emphasis on an exploratory approach, to better understand the sentiments, difficulties, and coping mechanisms of travel vloggers during the pandemic. The researchers are going to make use of the 5 indicators in the 15 videos total from 5 different vloggers that we are going to observe. We will gather information in connection to complete the comprehensiveness, relevance, timeliness, source expertise, and attitude. (a) Comprehensiveness refers to the completeness of the information on how they deal the pandemic and their ways. "The vlogger explain how to travel during pandemic, what are the requirements and situations to face" (b) Relevance means the vlogger's ability to stay connected when traveling to a desired location. "The vlogger has planned out the travel vacation when the lockdown was uplifted and tourist spots have reopened." (c) Timeliness refers to being timely in adjusting right away to the surroundings. "The vlogger was able to adjust to the recent changes in the surroundings." (d) Source expertise implies having the ability to give complete information in any type. "The vlogger has a complete and thorough explanation on the vlog." (e) Attitude defines how the vlogger reacts in the situation. "The vlogger grabbed the opportunity of experiencing what is the format for the new normal setting on touring when the local tourism has officially reopened."

The purpose of the study is to tackle the significant effects of covid-19 to the travel vloggers in the Philippines. Through it, it will answer the following questions:

- a. What is the significant predictors of travel vloggers in the Philippines in terms of the 5 indicators?
- b. Comparing the analysis of the experiences of the different travel vloggers in the Philippines

Through the observation where the researchers will watch the videos in order to gain more information then we are going to gather all the proofs from observing the 15 videos.

3. METHODOLOGY

A deductive method is going to be utilised in this research, with an emphasis on an exploratory approach pandemic. The researchers are going to make use of the 5 indicators (comprehensiveness, relevance, timeliness, source expertise, attitude) in the 8 videos that we are going to observe. We will gather information in connection to complete the said 5 indicators. In deductive reasoning, we need to determine whether the factors will allow us researchers to make a specific conclusion using logic. (Halpern, 2003; Evans, 2000). Formal logic defines the rules we must see in order to reach a confirmation. Deductive reasoning is often known as top-down processing.

The research design of this study is qualitative research and purposive sampling in which the researchers will rely on our own judgement in choosing the vloggers. Since the study focuses on observing the 15 videos from 5 different travel vloggers on Youtube basing on the 5 indicators (Comprehensiveness, Relevance, Timeliness, Source Expertise, Attitude).

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